

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

Annual Short Course

Special Session on University Transportation Infrastructure

October 17, 2019

The Characterization of Delamination Processes with Respect to Waterjet Shotcrete Removal during Tunnel Liner Repair and Maintenance

Josef Bourgeois & Erik Charrier (Ph.D. Students)
Hugh Miller (MN), John Steele (ME) & Brian Asbury (MN)

Mining Engineering Department
Colorado School of Mines

UNIVERSITY TRANSPORTATION CENTER
FOR UNDERGROUND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

COLORADO SCHOOL OF
MINES

Outline

- Project Introduction & Problem Statement
- Research Objective
- Scope of Work & Research Methodology
- Project Tasks and Schedule
- Testing & Data Collection
- Data Analysis
- Acknowledgements

Project Introduction

CSM Project Team: Hugh Miller (PI), Mining Engineering
John Steele (Co-PI), Mechanical Engineering
Brian Asbury (Research Associate), Mining Engineering
Erik Charrier (Ph.D. Student), Mining Engineering
Josef Bourgeois (Ph.D. Student), Mining Engineering
Devin Reasoner (Undergraduate), Mechanical Engineering

Contributing Partner: RAMAX LLC, SAI & IET Waterjet Foundation (CSM)

Laboratory Facilities: RAMAX/SAI Waterjet Laboratory, Lancaster, CA
CSM Earth Mechanics Institute (EMI)

Project Duration: May 15, 2017 – November 15, 2019
(currently revising final report)

Project Introduction

The repair of concrete/shotcrete liners that have been structurally compromised or damaged is a common activity associated with the maintenance and rehabilitation of tunnels and other types of underground workings. Unfortunately, conventional technologies used to excavate these damaged areas often possess inherent drawbacks related to safety, unintended collateral damage to the surrounding liner & substrate, and cost.

Project Introduction

There is significant potential for underground rehabilitation work to increase in prevalence due to current operating trends in underground construction, urban renewal, and infrastructure maintenance. This makes it crucial to investigate potential hazards.

Data below shows causes of occupational fatalities for underground non-coal mining locations between 2008 to 2017. It is difficult to find appropriate data for the underground construction industry however, causes of fatality in the mining industry can closely relate.

“NIOSH Mine and Mine Worker Charts | NIOSH | CDC.” [Online]. Available: <https://wwwn.cdc.gov/niosh-mining/MMWC>.

Project Introduction

Technical Concept: To circumvent the technical challenges associated with shotcrete removal using impact hammers, this project seeks to develop a unique system that utilizes waterjet technology as the primary excavation tool, where it has been hypothesized that waterjets can selectively remove damaged areas of support liners without structurally compromising or damaging intact material around the area being repaired.

“Chunnel Repairs Call On Conjet Hydrodemolition Robots,” Soc. Mining, Metall. Explor., 2009.

Research Objective

Empirically compare and contrast the unintended damage caused to the surrounding structural liner and substrate by conventional mechanical impact hammers and waterjet excavation methods during simulated liner repair, as well as quantify the extents and severity of this damage.

Project Impacts & Benefits

- Graduate and Undergraduate professional training and education
- Advance efforts to develop innovative, commercially viable technologies applicable to heavy construction, tunneling, and mining, with particular focus towards improving:
 - Occupational Safety & Health
 - Repair & Maintenance Operations (cost & time)
 - Effective Operating Life of UG Infrastructure & Workings
 - Environmental/Social Impacts
- To use this project to advance a research agenda in waterjet applications in tunnel rehabilitation and excavation

Operational Characteristics: Waterjet Excavation

An alternative approach with the rehabilitation of bridge decks is substituting mechanical impact hammers with hydrodemolition.

Advantages

- Leaves the substrate deck clean
- Removes corrosion from rebar without causing damage
- Minimizes vibrations
- Avoids microfracturing
- Removes lower strength/deteriorated concrete
- Leaves rough, irregular surface profile

While there are significant differences in the excavation layout, operating characteristics, and environmental characteristics between bridge decks and underground structural liners, advantages show potential to apply similar technology to liners for rehabilitation purposes.

<https://conjet.com/method/hydrodemolition/>

<https://www.forconstructionpros.com/concrete/article/21049078/robots-accelerate-utahs-largest-hydrodemolition-bridge-repair>

UNIVERSITY TRANSPORTATION CENTER
FOR UNDERGROUND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

Operational Characteristics: Waterjet Excavation

- Ability to Focus Energy
- Continuous Operation
- No Direct Rock Contact
- Omni-Directional
- Mechanically Simple
- Highly Flexible
- Amenable to Remote Robotic Control
- No Dust or Gas Generation
- No Spark or Gas Ignition Source
- Selective Excavation Process
- Extremely Mobile
- Can Efficiently be Adapted for Varied Geology and Applications
- Numerous Variations of the Technology

Research Methodology

- Literature Search
- Testing Methodology & Selection of System Parameters
- Laboratory & Equipment Set-up (EMI & RAMAX Waterjet Lab)
- Sensors & Data Acquisition System
- Physical testing on engineered and instrumented shotcrete panels designed to quantify the following:
 - delamination/loss of adhesion;
 - stress distribution; and
 - fracture propagation associated with mechanical impacts and waterjet impingement.
- Pre & Post Assessment of the Damage to the Shotcrete/Substrate Interface
- Data Analysis
- Completion of Final Report & Journal Publications

Project Tasks

- Literature search
- Testing methodology & selection of system parameters
- Engineering & design of motion system, test panels & panel frame
- Sensors & data acquisition systems
- Equipment selection, fabrication & assembly
- Laboratory set-up (EMI & RAMAX Waterjet Laboratory)
- Construction of engineered and instrumented shotcrete panels with reinforced concrete substrate
- Testing of sensors and data acquisition system
- Pre-testing: GPR surveys of each test panel
- Mechanical impact tests & assessment
- Waterjet impact tests & assessment
- Vibration analysis
- Post-testing: GPR surveys of each test panel
- GPR data analysis
- Final report & journal publications/conference presentations
 - **Final report currently undergoing revisions**
 - **PhD dissertation currently underway (projected completion date: December 2020)**

Testing & Data Collection – Test Panels

Testing & Data Collection – Data Acquisition System

Testing & Data Collection – Ground Penetrating Radar

GSSI 2600 MHz Radar Antenna coupled with SIR 3000 Radar System Control Unit

Testing & Data Collection – Mechanical Testing

Testing & Data Collection – Waterjet Testing

Data Analysis – Quantitative Vibration Data

Mechanical Excavation Panel 3
(Panel 3 Hammer 6)

Waterjet Cut Panel 2
(Day2 Panel1 Row2 Cut1)

Data Analysis – Qualitative Visual Inspection

Data Analysis – Qualitative Processed GPR Scans

Mechanical
Excavation
Panel 2
GPR
Analysis

Pre-Test

Post-Test

Waterjet
Excavation
Test Panel
GPR
Analysis

Final Project Status

- All project tasks up to Final Report have been completed
- Project team is currently undergoing revisions of Final Report
- Supplemental work is being conducted with this research for a PhD dissertation scheduled for completion in December 2020

Acknowledgement(s)

- Support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) is gratefully acknowledged.
- Support from RAMEX LLC, SAI, Inc., and IET Foundation
- Assistance, guidance & support provided by:
 - Dr. Jamal Rostami
 - Dr. F.D. Wang
 - Dr. E. Nebeker
 - Dr. Priscilla Nelson
 - Mr. Brent Duncan
 - Dr. Marte Gutierrez

Thank You

Contact Information

Josef Bourgeois
Ph.D. Student
Mining Engineering Department
Colorado School of Mines
1600 Illinois St.
Golden, CO 80401
Tel. (720) 690-7089
Email. jobourge@mines.edu

Hugh B. Miller
Associate Professor
Mining Engineering Department
Colorado School of Mines
1600 Illinois St.
Golden, CO USA 80401
Tel. (303) 273-3558
Email. hbmiller@mines.edu

